

This is the metadata corresponding to the publication:

Castroviejo-Fisher, S., Padial, J.M., De la Riva, I., Pombal Jr, J.P., da Silva, H.R., Rojas-Runjaic, F.J., Medina-Méndez, E., Frost, D.R. (2015) Phylogenetic systematics of egg-brooding frogs (Anura: Hemiphractidae) and the evolution of direct development. *Zootaxa* 4004, 1–75.
10.11646/zootaxa.4004.1.1

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